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UNLOCKING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH: A DATA ANALYTICS FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN THE MOLDOVAN WINE SECTOR

Abstract: the development of the wine sector is a priority of the national policy of the Republic of Moldova. Given the importance of this sector for the Moldovan economy, its sustainable development should be carefully planned and constantly adapted to emerging innovations in this field. Analytics is an important consideration in developing strategic directions for the sector, and has been changing significantly over the past few years due to the impact of advanced technology. New tools allow the development of many alternative approaches that will be relevant to different strategic approaches.

Keywords: wine sector, analytics, communication strategies, optimization.

Introduction. The wine industry is an important part of Moldova's economy, and the country aims to strengthen its position on the world stage by positioning itself as the "Global Wine Capital 2025". To achieve sustainable growth and increase

competitiveness, effective communication strategies based on data analytics are needed. This work presents a data analytics framework aimed at optimizing wineries' communications with consumers and supporting the sustainable development of the industry.

Analysis of the current state and challenges of the Moldovan wine industry.

Viticulture in Moldova is represented by a significant number of economic agents - 40970 (natural and legal persons, joint stock companies, peasant farms), owning 78,783 plots of vineyards intended for wine production. However, there is a tendency to reduce the area of vineyards used for winemaking by about 3% per year, which requires attention to sustainable development. Moreover, the age structure of vineyards is a cause for concern: of the 47.7 thousand hectares registered with SIA RVV, only 19% are young plantations (up to 15 years old), while almost 50% exceed the age of 21 years, which reduces their production potential and resilience to climate change (Fig.1).

The crisis is also affecting production volumes: 179,000 tons of grapes will be processed in 2024, 32% less than in 2023, and the output of wine materials decreased by 34% to 11.7 million decaliters, one of the lowest figures in the last decade.

The industry thus faces systemic challenges, from aging vineyards and land degradation to climate risks and declining production. This requires the urgent implementation of sustainable and digital solutions, including precision farming, support for new varieties, and better communication with markets.

Wine exports play a key role for the industry. There is a positive trend in 2024, with exports in volume increasing by 17% and in value by 22% compared to 2023. At the same time, still wines dominate the export structure (55%), while wines with a protected geographical indication (IGP) have a smaller share.

The analysis of consumer behavior shows that 70% of the urban population of Moldova aged 18-70 years consumed alcoholic beverages in the last 6 months. Wine is a popular choice: 25% of consumers prefer still wine, 40% - sparkling wine, and 48% - house wine. When choosing wine, consumers focus simultaneously on the following 5 factors: brand (40%), sugar content (35%), variety/color (33%), producer/brand (30%), previous experience (30%), and price/promotions (29%) (Fig.2).

Forecast of areas (thousand hectares) for the next 10 years

Suprafetele de vita de vie soiuri pentru vin
in scadere (-3%/ anual, cca. -1,9 mii.ha.)

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Fig.1: Evolution of vineyard areas in commercial production farms in bearing stage, thousand hectares

Source: developed by the authors based on presented data

Fig.2: Top 5 Factors in Choosing Wine

Source: developed by the author based on presented data

Despite positive export performance, the industry faces communication challenges. Competition in the market is high and consumers have a wide choice of wines, including imported wines. It is important to note that 80% of consumers consider Moldovan wines to be of higher quality than wines from Italy (60%), France (52%), Spain (38%) and Romania (25%).

Data analytics framework for optimizing communication strategies. The implementation of a data analytics framework based on the principles of digital transformation of the agri-food sector is proposed to improve marketing efficiency and sustainable growth of the Moldovan wine industry. In the context of increased competition and fragmentation of consumer attention, especially among young people and online audiences, the analytical approach allows to move from generalized communication to point, personalized interaction.

Data analytics framework for optimizing communication strategies. The implementation of a data analytics framework based on the principles of digital transformation of the agri-food sector is proposed to improve marketing efficiency and sustainable growth of the Moldovan wine industry. In the context of increased competition and fragmentation of consumer attention, especially among young people and online audiences, the analytical approach allows to move from generalized communication to point, personalized interaction. Analytical results are integrated into strategic planning - from the development of advertising campaigns to the formation of pricing and discount policies. Practical tools include A/B testing, email marketing, retargeting and loyalty programs adapted to the

local context and consumer mentality. Special attention should be paid to the integration of user-generated content (UGC) and the engagement of local influencers that reinforce brand trust. At the same time, it is critical to implement monitoring of the effectiveness of strategies through key indicators - growth in repeat purchases, engagement levels, average check - and flexible adjustments based on the principles of the PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) continuous cycle.

Thus, the analytical framework becomes not just an auxiliary tool, but the foundation of strategic brand management in the context of high competition, unstable demand and growing consumer expectations.

Application Potential and Expected Results. The application of the framework will allow wine companies to target their marketing efforts more precisely, optimize communication channels and increase consumer loyalty. This, in turn, will contribute to increased sales in both domestic and international markets. For example, data analysis may reveal that online channels and loyalty programs are particularly important for attracting young consumers.

5. Conclusion. The proposed data analysis framework provides the Moldovan wine industry with a powerful tool for optimizing communication strategies. Its implementation will contribute to sustainable growth, increase competitiveness and strengthen the position of Moldovan wines on the world stage. The improvement of analytical tools, as well as the introduction of other innovative methods and technologies for analysing, interpreting data, as well as new approaches and products should help wine enterprises from the Republic of Moldova to strengthen themselves on the national and international markets.

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METODE DE STUDIU ȘI CERCETARE INTUITIVĂ DE CREAȚIE

"Cea mai necesară sarcină a civilizației este să învențe oamenii să gândească. Dar cel mai important păcat este că societatea se declară satisfăcută cu lucrurile așa cum sunt. Nu va fi un progres până când nu vor fi destui nesatisfăcuți - și acest lucru poate fi realizat numai când ei vor fi aduși să gândească dincolo de limitele cu care sunt obișnuiți"

Thomas Alva EDISON

Introducere. Componenta principală a creației o constituie imaginația, dar creația de valoare reală mai presupune și o motivație, dorința de a realiza ceva nou, ceva deosebit. Și cum noutatea, valoarea azi, nu se obține cu ușurință, o altă componentă este voința, perseverența în a face numeroase încercări și verificări.

Demersurile, procedurile, tehnicile și metodele de creație tehnico-economică constituie mijloace de eficientizare a proceselor creative. Performanța se bazează pe demersuri euristice, tehnici și metode de creație care se îmbină succesiv. Metodele intuitive (psihologice) se bazează mai puțin pe logica gândirii umane și mai mult pe activizarea capacităților creatoare ale inventatorului, pe intuiție, fantezie, afinitate față de analogii și metafore, pe capacitatea de conlucrare a conștientului cu subconștientul, pe implicarea laturii emoționale a spiritului, etc.

1. Asocierea consonantă. Asocierea denumită de Alex Osborn ca fiind un “*procedeu fundamental pentru producția de idei*”, reprezintă o *funcție* a intelectului